

USING AUDIOVISUAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING THE HISTORY OF WEAPONS

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Annotation . The article states the significance and features of audiovisual media in the process of teaching the history of weapons . The author analyzes the experience of famous teachers in the use of audiovisual teaching aids in modern conditions.

Key words: audiovisual teaching aids , teaching the history of weapons , methods of teaching history.

In connection with the process of information globalization in the world , the field of education is constantly changing. Massive updating and creation of learning technologies is an important request and requirement of modern society. In a dynamically changing world, students of higher education educational institutions give greater preference to studying academic disciplines with the help of innovative technologies. High-quality prepared material and information and communication technologies make it possible to familiarize students with the necessary information quickly and effectively. Speaking about the introduction of new technologies into the learning process, it is important to note the significance and specificity of the principle of audiovisual clarity.

In a world where there is a focus on the visual component, improving the results of the pedagogical process is possible with the use of audiovisual teaching aids. Audiovisual teaching aids are a group of technical teaching aids, including visual, auditory and visual-auditory technologies [1]. Studying the history of weapons becomes more effective thanks to the introduction of audiovisual aids that successfully allow one to assimilate the material. In pedagogical science, audio- visual teaching aids are divided into traditional and modern. Traditional audiovisual technologies include handouts and demonstrations of teaching aids. Modern audiovisual teaching aids contain methodological, specially processed material, which is very often used in higher military educational institutions when studying the course on the history of military affairs . In the practice of many teachers, one can find the use of documentaries or feature films, but they are not educational, although they can be part of the educational process.

For a convenient selection of the necessary audiovisual teaching aids that meet the requirements of the training programs in a particular discipline, it is necessary to develop "Video lessons" for these academic disciplines . It includes various historical materials, presentations, as well as assignments and tests. It is important to note that this complex is not leading in the learning process, but is only used as an addition to the teacher's pedagogical activities in the classroom.

A popular means of audiovisual clarity is information and reference technologies. These include multimedia reference books and interactive encyclopedias. For example, the " Weapons " encyclopedia contains historical articles, animated illustrations, maps, and various

video clips necessary for better assimilation of historical material on the topic “the history of the creation of Weapons . ” Such audiovisual teaching aids complement the process of training and education of the future officer - Defender of his Motherland .

It should be noted that it is very important for a teacher to collect his own library and catalog of various types of audiovisual teaching aids, both educational and non-educational. Audiovisual clarity will provide the opportunity to solve problem problems and successfully achieve the goals and objectives set in the lesson.

The experience of practicing teachers is of significant value for pedagogical science. Many teachers popularize audiovisual teaching aids and offer their own improvements to technologies already used in practice. Thus, it is proposed to develop and put into use multimedia history classrooms, considering possible prospects for the development of pedagogy with the help of this innovative technology [2]. In addition , many experts attached particular importance to the use of information and communication means of education in teaching the history of weapons .

Thus, learning through audiovisual technology is changing the face of education. The process of teaching the history of weapons becomes more effective using new teaching tools. Teachers should never underestimate their own sense of creativity and seek, develop, and create new technologies and methods to enrich pedagogical science.

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